

AGRO4AGRI

Welcome to the workshop

Pathways to Impact in Sustainable Agrochemistry

A 360° Innovation Approach from Lab to Market

3Bs Materials Conference, Lisbon

Friday 10th April 2026 08.45 – 12:30 CEST

Moderator: Lesley Tobin, OPTIMAT UK

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The Project

€5.3M Horizon Europe project

Biobased nano-materials for agriculture

12 partners | **7** countries

The Problem

Conventional agrochemicals are inefficient

A large share never reaches the plant

High cost.
Environmental impact

This Session

From science to scale-up to market

4 talks + 2 expert panels

Focus on sustainability and real-world uptake

Join the Discussion

Open discussion

Questions and contributions welcome

Your perspective matters

- A very appreciative 'thank you in advance' to our speakers and panellists – and to you for coming along
- Enjoy the workshop

Lesley Tobin
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AGRO4AGRI

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invitations to exclusive events

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09:00 – 10:50

PART 1 - Presentations 90 mins:

Moderator: Lesley Tobin, Senior Consultant at Optimat

09:00 – 09:20

Dr. Elena Usala, Researcher at AINIA (Spain)

Nanocellulose-Based Advanced Fertilizer Systems for Controlled Nutrient Release in Sustainable Agriculture.

09:20 – 09:40

Dr. Inmaculada Ortiz, Researcher at CTC – Fundación Centro Tecnológico de Componentes (Spain).

Engineering Forest-derived Biochar as a Nanoplatfrom for Sustainable Nutrient Delivery in Plants.

09:40 – 10:00

Dr. Alba Somoza Cerviño, R&D Business Unit Process Engineer at SYSPRO (Spain).

Industrial perspectives: scaling and commercialisation of bio-based agrochemicals.

10:00 – 10:30

10:30 – 10:50

Dr. Jolanta Beinaroviča, Senior Business Strategy Consultant at OPTIMAT (UK).

Stakeholder-aligned pathways to impact and exploitation in sustainable agrochemistry.

10:50 – 12:30

PART 2 - Expert Panel Discussions

Chair: Dr. Jolanta Beinaroviča, Senior Business Strategy Consultant at OPTIMAT

Panel 1: From Frameworks to Field Decisions: Making Sustainability Actionable in Agriculture

Panel 2: Biobased Innovation in Practice: Stakeholder Expectations, Barriers, and Enablers

Elena Usala - *R&D Project Specialist, AINIA Technological Centre*

Elena's work focuses on nanocellulose and biopolymer-based materials, from agricultural waste streams through to advanced manufacturing applications including bioprinting.

She brings to this workshop a **hands-on perspective on translating sustainable bio-based materials into practical, scalable solutions.**

Inmaculada Ortiz - *Researcher & Project Manager, Technological Centre CTC*

Inmaculada holds a PhD in Chemistry and has carried out research at the International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory and Nova University Lisbon. Her expertise is in the design and functionalisation of organic and inorganic nanomaterials for industrial applications.

She sheds a **rigorous materials-science perspective on how nanomaterial innovations navigate the path to real-world use.**

Alba Somoza Cerviño - *Process Engineer (R&D Unit), SYSPRO Automation S.L.*

Alba is a chemical engineer with experience across both academia and industry, working on process design, scale-up, and formulation development in areas including specialty chemicals and sustainable resource recovery. She holds a PhD that led to a patented formulation, and has contributed to regional, national, and European R&D projects.

She places a **practical, scale-up-focused lens to the question of how lab-stage innovations become deployable processes.**

Dr Jolanta Beinarovica - *Senior Business Strategy Consultant, Optimat; Exploitation Mger & Chair of the Innovation Committee, AGRO4AGRI*

Jolanta specialises in technology commercialisation across life sciences, agriculture, and engineering biology. With a PhD in synthetic biology and over five years supporting innovators with investment readiness and market strategy, she has worked with more than 140 companies.

She brings a **sharp, practical perspective on stakeholder-aligned pathways to impact.**